

LEAD GLASS FIBRE MADE FROM ELECTRONIC WASTE

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SUMMARY: Properties of continuous glass fibres produced on the base of tv-tube glass waste on laboratory and industrial scales are investigated. The thermal-viscous constants tv-glass are relatively small and mechanical properties of fibres are slightly worth compared with E-glass fibres but chemical resistance especially in acid is high due to the heal effect of acid treatment as well as stability of the silica lattice. High amount of lead oxide in the fibres based on the mixture of socket and neck parts of tv-tube waste allows to reach an attenuation of radiation of about 40 % in the neutron field and about 20% in the photon field for test specimen produced using such fibre as reinforced element of composites with polymer matrix. Development of composites is of course only possible via proper combinations of such fibre and corresponded matrix.

KEYWORDS: lead, glass, television glass, waste recycling, fibre, radiation shielding

INTRODUCTION

The problem of nature conservation, rational using of raw materials, decreasing of consumption of raw materials for the production of industrial unit, is directly connected to waste disposal. At the present time only in Germany 260 million tons of waste is produced, including 1.5 million tons of electronic waste [1]. Recycling of electronic waste usually is limited to collection and separation into different kind of materials which then either may be used once more in the industrial circle or must be deposited in a special dump protected from influence of environment [2]. Last one concerns such parts of waste that contain

ecologically risky components. In the television and computer glass tubes such parts as socket, plumb and neck contain a high amount of PbO that may vary depending on producer, year of production and quality of separation during recycling. Usually amount of PbO in the socket part of tv-tube lies in the range between 10 and 23 wt.%, in the neck part - between 1 and 34 wt.% and plumb part that fulfills a role of solder between screen and socket parts of picture tube may contain up to 75 wt.% PbO. Screen glass is free of PbO but in some composition the presence of SrO up to 8 wt.% is possible [2, 3]. For screen glass of tv-tube it seems that the way is found to bring it back for remelting after careful separation from the other parts. Lead contained parts of tv-tube are critical from the point of reuse for the production of tv-tube and need to be either put in a special dump or recycled into a product compatible with environment. Taking into account that glass waste has a large amount of ecoincompatible elements in the structure transformation of them into glassy or crystallized state may not serve as a full guarantee to keep heavy elements for a long time. The reason for that is the nature of such elements as lead or strontium. These elements have a tendency not enter the crystal phase due to the large radius of cation and stay in glass. From the other side this kind of waste is an excellent raw material for the production of continuous glass fibres both from whole glass tube cullet and mixture of other glass parts of the tv-tube glass waste separated from the screen [4-6].

In this context glass fibre may be an alternative decision for recycling of tv-glass waste because fibre could be more protected from any contact with external environment as reinforced element of composites having polymer or other matrix. Possibility of production of continuous glass fibres seems to be contrary to the doubts of some experts concerned the keeping of a constant level of viscosity needed for glass fibre production [2]. But one should try via doing and our experience as well as results of other groups are the confirmation of it.

Manufacture of continuous glass fibres based on tv-tube glass waste makes more sense from the point of new unknown chemical composition of such fibres. Up to know so called lead glass fibre (L-glass) is well-known it has advantage of radiation protection and is suitable for use in X-ray technologist gowns and as a tracer yarn in the composites where nondestructive X-ray examination can verify fibre alignment [7]. L-glass fibres are produced from silicate glass with about 59 wt.% of PbO via drawing process and need a preparation of the batch and use of expensive components. Bulk lead glasses for radiation protection contain up to 79 wt. % of PbO and is not useful for fibre production. At the same time exists a big demand for radiation shielding materials. Glass fibres from electronic waste introduced into composite with controlled selection of binder and matrix phase could help to cover a wide-band of waves and to form a requested shape of the end-product.

Detailed investigation of the properties of continuous glass fibres based on tv-tube glass waste by itself and their application for composites opens a new kind of glass fibre for the market as well as makes a step towards development of composites with special properties in the field of radiation protection. This work is an attempt to design of new composites via combination the advantages of waste disposal with new fibres as recycling product.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The following kinds of glass fibre were investigated:

- glass fibre, produced on the laboratory scale from the mixture of all parts of tv-tube glass waste (Firm Schott, Germany)

- glass fibre, produced on the laboratory scale from the screen glass and from the mixture of socket and neck parts of tv-tube glass waste (tv-tube glass factory, Volnogorsk, Ukraine)
- glass fibre, produced on the industrial scale from the mixture of neck and socket part of tv-tube glass waste (Firm LS GmbH; Leuna, Germany).

For comparison E-glass textile fibres (EC9-600 tex TS, Firm h.k.o., Germany) were used. Chemical composition of investigated fibres is shown in the Table 1.

Table 1: Chemical composition of glass fibres produced from tv-tube glass waste

Oxide	Mixture of all parts of tv-tube, Firm Schott (Germany)	Mixture of socket and neck glass, Firm LS, Leuna (Germany)	Glass factory for production tv-tubes, Volnogorsk (Ukraine)		E-glass [8]
			screen glass	socket+neck glass	
SiO ₂	56	51.1-60.15	64.1	60.2	55.2
TiO ₂	0.2	0.03-0.075	0.4	-	-
Al ₂ O ₃	2.5	1.55-4.5	3.2	3.6	14.8
B ₂ O ₃	0.2	tr.	-	-	7.3
CaO	1.9	2.1-5.95	2.0	5.5	16.7
MgO	0.4	2.6-3.0	-	2.5	3.3
SrO	5.9	0-0.2	10.0	-	-
BaO	6.5	0.75-1.9	3.0	2.2	-
PbO	9.1	9.9-23.5	-	10.5	-
Sb ₂ O ₃	0.4	0.05-0.2	0.4	0.4	-
ZrO ₂	1.2	0.02-0.025	-	-	-
Na ₂ O	11.7	5.4-6.55	7.8	5.5	0.3
K ₂ O	6.1	8.7-9.85	8.0	9	0.2
Rest	0.74	0.203-	1.1	0.5	0.6
Na ₂ O ₄ /Al ₂ O ₃	4.68	1.2-4.22	2.43	1.53	0.02
Si/O	0.39	0.41-0.76	0.44	0.43	0.31

On the laboratory scale glass fibres were drawn through a single nozzle Pt-10%Rh feeder, placed in the electrical oven, where the conditions of fibre-drawing could be imitated. Industrial test of fibre production was fulfilled for the mixture of socket and neck part of tv-tube and performed at the Lauscha Fibre International GmbH (Germany) [9]. Fibre tape device was used as a main equipment for production of continuous glass

Chemical durability of glass fibres was determined by the weight loss (%) of a sample treated under different conditions and compared with leaching behaviour of E-glass fibres.

For mechanical tests, 100 single fibres were pasted one by one onto a 10 x 10 mm paper frame and their diameters were measured by optical microscope to an accuracy of $\pm 0,5$ mm.

Morphological changes both of glass fibre surface and glass fibre section before and after treatment in chemical mediums were studied by raster electron microscopy (REM). The compositions of leached layers were determined by energy dispersive x-ray analysis (EDX). The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and the beam was rastered over an area of approximately 0,5 mm² in order to avoid beam-induced

compositional changes. X-ray intensities of K, L and M- lines of correspondingly elements were counted simultaneously for 100 s. Quantitative analysis of surfaces was made at 20 kV, going step by step from the edge of fibre to the centre. The glass fibre sections were prepared by embedding them into epoxy resin and hardening, with subsequent polishing and coating by gold or carbon.

Differential thermal analysis (DTA) was used for the determination of crystallisation effects and phase transformation in glasses and fibres.

Investigation of absorption of neutron radiation was fulfilled at the medical equipment where average energy of neutron reaches 5.8 MeV, produced from 14 MeV deuterons (Firm Studsvik, Neutron Dose Rate Meter 2202 D) and then verified according to German Standard for radiation protection [10]. Attenuation of photon energy was tested at laboratory device for Cs¹³⁷ (E=0.661 MeV) and Co⁶⁰ (E=1.251 MeV). As a model specimen glass plate melted from the mixture of all parts of tv-tube and mixture of socket and neck of tv-tube were prepared.

Fibre reinforced composites were produced via impregnation of epoxy resin with silane coupling agent of glass fibres produced on the base of the mixture of socket and neck parts of tv-tubes as well as E-glass fibre fabric. As a test sample also the polyethylene (Hostalen GUR 4120; Firm Ticona) filled with tv-glass powder (mixture of socket and neck parts) in amount of about 40 vol.% was prepared by sintering at 185°C.

RESULT OF EXPERIMENT AND DISCUSSION

On laboratory scale continuous glass fibres were formed from the mixture both whole parts of tv-tube and socket+neck of tv-tube with uniformed diameter varied from 4.5 µm to 20 µm depending on drawing speed. The high fibre-form ability makes it possible to draw fibres with small diameters that usually contain fewer defects on the surface and have a high strength. For tv-glass fibres the tensile strength is comparably the data of E-glass fibres. This might be explained only by absence of surface defects, because the chemical composition of tv-glass waste and specially content of PbO lead usually to diminution of mechanical properties of glass [3].

Chemical resistance of tv-glass fibres treated at 98°C for 3 hours in 2n HCl and 2n NaOH are shown in the Table 2. One can see that the resistance of tv-glass fibre in acid medium is much higher than for E-glass fibres, destruction of tv-glass fibres made from whole parts of tube reaches about 30 wt.%; fibres based on the mixture of socket and neck glass are more proof in alkali even than E-glass fibres.

Table 2: Properties of glass fibres produced from tv-tube glass waste on laboratory plant

Fibre type	Density [g/cm ³]	Diameter [µm]	Tensile strength [MPa]	Corrosive loss in [wt. %]	
				2n HCl	2n NaOH
Mixture of whole parts of tv-tube	2.6 - 2.7	4.5 - 20	2130-2470	1.5	32.7
Mixture of socket and neck of tv-tube	2.9 - 3.1	4.5 - 20	2200-3000	5.0	5.72
E-glass fibre (Firm	2.53 - 2.55	7.9 - 10.5	2150-2600	46.1	17

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These results may be explained using the formula of Huggins [11] for the Si/O ratio (Table 1). For tv-glass based on the mixture of whole parts of tv-tube this ratio is changed from 0.39 to 0.76 and fibres from these glasses show a high chemical resistance in acid due to the stability of the silica lattice [12]. For E-glass the data is low and equal to 0,31 and they undergo the corrosion in acid medium. It is known [13] that the aluminium ion in fourfold coordination goes in the glass network and improves the resistance towards acids. This could be possible if the ratio $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 > 1$ [14]. For investigated tv-glass, this ratio is changed from 1.2 to 4.68 and one may suspect that even the low content of Al-ions (Table 1) affects the stability of glass lattice and as a consequence of that follows the rising of chemical resistance.

We tried to confirm these suggestions by investigations of the surface and sections of tv-glass fibre (mixture of whole parts of tv-tube) before and after treatment in acid and alkali mediums. Initial fibres have relatively clean surface, without defects and big difference in chemical composition between the edge and the centre (Fig.1).

a

b

Fig. 1: REM micrograph (a) and EDX analysis (b) of initial tv-glass fibres

After treatment in 2n NaOH glass fibres were corroded and built the porous coat that could be easy broken (Fig. 2, a). EDX analysis shows that oxides of Na, K, Ba, Sr, Pb are leached out cladding glass of fibres compared to the initial fibre (Fig. 2, b). One may observe the three zones in the fibre structure and the tendency to dissolving the network of glass under alkali

b

a

Fig. 2.: REM micrograph (a) and EDX analysis (b) of tv-glass fibres after leaching in 2n NaOH for 3 h

action. In acid medium tv-glass fibres have a smooth surface, and they keep the initial size (Fig. 3, a). This could be the reason for improving of mechanical properties. The acid action develops only in a slight healing of surface defects. The main network forming elements are in glass and it confirms the theoretical conclusions(Fig. 3, b). It might be also a way to improvement of the mechanical properties of tv-glass fibres by treatment in acid solutions.

a

b

Fig. 3: REM micrograph (a) and EDX analysis (b) of tv-glass fibres after leaching in 2n HCl for 3 h. Fibre produced on industrial plant have diameter in the range from 8.7 to 25 μm and compared with E-glass fibre do have lower data of thermal -viscous constants due to the high content of lead oxide in the mixture of socket and neck parts of tv-tube glass waste (Table 3). Mechanical properties of this kind of fibres are also low compared with E-glass fibre but may be sufficient for the production of textiles.

Table 3: Properties of glass and glass fibres in comparison

Property	E-glass	Socket+neck waste glass	L-glass fibre, [15, 16]
Density [g/cm^3]	2.55-2.62	2.75-3.10	4.2-4.3
Tensile Strength [MPa]	3100-3800	2295-3400	1680
Elastic Modulus [GPa]	76-78 (fibre) 82.5-82.8 (bulk)	61-62 (fibre) 67.7-67.9 (bulk)	51 (fibre)
Thermal Linear Expansion, 20-300°C [$^{\circ}\text{C}\times 10^6$]	5.4	9.8	-
Poisson's Ratio	0.22-0.24	0.19-0.21	-
T_g [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] ($\eta=10^{13.3}$ dPa s)	640	447	-
Softening Point [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] ($\eta=10^{7.6}$ dPa s)	830-870	565	-
Liquidus Temp. [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	1140	990	1118
Fiberizing Temp. [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] ($\eta=10^3$ dPa s)	1200	1190	-

Hydrolytic Resistance (water) [Class, ml 0.01n HCl]	Class 3 (0.27)	Class 3 (0.65)	-
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Analysis of the properties of tv-glass fibres shows the capability for their application for reinforcement of composite with polymeric matrix. It is known that the E-glass fibres are used already a long time for reinforcement of polymer-based composites [17]. The incorporation of nearly 30% of E-glass fibre in polypropylene matrix increases the E-modules and bending strength [17].

Taking into consideration the fact that tv-glass fibres have relatively high strength, low diameter and need only 1400°C for remelting, they could be a good rival for E-glass fibres on the fibre market. Especially from the point of keeping environment and natural recourses it is of interest, because stage of preperation of glass batch is excluded as well as a necessity in an expensive equipment for the purification of exhaust gases during melting.

High amount of heavy metals in the glass fibres based on tv-tube waste leads to look for a special application of them such as L-glass (lead glass) which has the advantage of radiation protection [7]. It is suitable for use in X-ray technologist' gowns and as a tracer yarn in composites where nondestructive x-ray examination can verify fiber alignment. L-glass fibres are produced from silicate glass with about 59 wt.% lead oxide via drawing process but it needs preparation of the batch and use of expensive components. Mathematical calculation of the absorption coefficient for glass made from electronic waste in comparison with L-glass and metallic lead shows that it may be possible to consider them as an element for the purpose of design of fibre reinforced shielding radiation composites (Fig. 4). Lead glass with an amount of lead oxide up to 79% is not useful for fibre production, but at the same time exists a big demand for production of materials with protective properties and complicated shape. In the case that glass fibres from electronic waste are introduced into composite with controlled selection of binder and matrix phase a broad radiation spectrum could be covered and a requested shape of the end-product may be formed.

Fig. 4: Calculated absorption coefficients of glass made from electronic glass waste compared with well-know materials depending on radioactive energy

Using calculated data as the base, some provisional tests for estimation of radiation absorption were performed:

- absorption of photon-radiation emitted by Cs¹³⁷ and Co⁶⁰
- and

- absorption of neutron radiation.

Results of these investigations were performed as absorption coefficient μ , tenth-value thickness (ZWD) and mass attenuation coefficient.

Absorption coefficient μ is calculated from the following equations [19]:

where I_0 = the initial intensity of the radiation; I = the intensity after passage through the substance; d = the thickness of the absorbing substance. Absorption coefficient μ is a function of the wave length of the electromagnetic waves and the chemical and physical nature of the absorbing substance.

Tenth-value thickness (d_{ZWD}) is a thickness of radiation shield that downgrades the dose rate to 1/10 [20]:

As materials do have different densities for several applications weight is a more critical point than thickness - clothes or doors for example. To protect one square meter more or less mass is needed. In this case, ZWM is the mass per unit area of absorbing material, necessary to diminish the incoming energy to a tenth of its initial value (Fig. 5)

Absorption coefficients measured for the bulk glass specimen made from the mixture of all parts of tv-tube as well as mixture of socket+neck parts in the photon field are shown in the Table 4.

Table 4: Absorption coefficient of tv-glasses in comparison under photon-radiation in the field of Cs¹³⁷ and Co⁶⁰

Kind of glass	Absorption coefficient μ [cm^{-1}]	
	Cs ¹³⁷ (E=0.661 MeV)	Co ⁶⁰ (E=1.251 MeV)
Mixture of all parts of tv-tube	0.126	0.134
Mixture of socket and neck of tv-tube	0.253	0.172
Lead plate	0.533	0.967
Lead plate [21]	0.660	1.150

Under photon-radiation the better results are shown by a glass composition based on mixture of socket and neck of tv-tube due to the relatively high content of lead oxide (up to 24 wt.%).

Due to the fact the highest priorities in the nuclear industry have materials with complex radiation shielding, for example, working against both photon and neutron radiation, this requirement may meet only composites. That is why it was decided to try to design a composite reinforced or filled with respective elements that are introduced in the plastic matrix. In this case heavy metals such as lead or barium in glass may work against photon radiation and materials that are composed of hydrogen or carbon, such polyethylene, paraffin, water or graphite would serve against neutron radiation.

Following composites' materials were made:

- epoxy resin reinforced both with E-glass fibres and with glass fibre made from the mixture of socket and neck part of tv-tube;

and

- polyethylene filled with powder glass based on the mixture of socket and neck of tv-tube.

The materials were tested in the photon and neutron spectrum of radiation. The results are shown at the Fig. 5.

Composites filled with tv-glass waste show a relatively light improvement of shielding in the photon field compared to iron or composites filled with E-glass. Real efficiency is shown in the neutron field of radiation. The materials based on tv-glass waste and polyethylene may be compatible with paraffin keeping the same level of energies but having better mechanical and thermal properties and lower weight. That is important for construction of protective elements such door, tube, vessels, etc. Development of composites based on tv-glass wastes is attractive from the economic point of view as well as ecological protection. To meet the requirements of a final product more information are necessary, that may be topic for further investigations.

Glass fibres and composites based on electronic waste could serve as a good example of a recycling product that has relatively low costs for remelting and production as well as an advanced application like radiation protection.

Fig. 5: Degree of attenuation by different composites compared to standard materials

CONCLUSIONS

Continuous glass fibres based on tv-tube glass waste show relatively small thermal-viscous constant and slightly low mechanical properties compared to E-glass fibres but are suitable for using for textile processing. The healing effect of the fibre surface and high resistance in 2n HCl is observed. Tv-glass fibres exhibit to have a considerable promise as reinforced element of composites with polymer matrix shielding of neutron and photon radiation.

REFERENCES

1. Ondracek, G., "Werkstofftechnische Abfallbehandlung und Entsorgung über remineralisierte Recyclingprodukte mit Multibarrierstruktur", *Berg- und Hüttenmanische Monatshefte*, No. 7, 1994, pp. 273-279.
2. Lindig, M., "Recycling von Fernsehglas", *Glastechnische Berichte, Glass Science and Technology*, Vol. 67, No. 9, 1994, pp. N 95-97.
3. Volf, M. B., "Technical Approach to Glass", *Glass Science and Technology*, Vol. 10, Elsevier, Amsterdam, Oxford, New York, Tokyo, 1990.
4. Kravtchenko, I. A., Nitsche, R. and Ondracek, G., "Verfahren und Vorrichtung zum Recycling von Glasabfällen", *German Patent*, P 4332532, 1993.
5. Clasen, R., Kravtchenko, I. A. and Ondracek, G., "Recycling von Abfallgläsern über einen Faserziehprozeß", *Kurzreferate der 68. glastechnischen Tagung*, Deutsche Glastechnische Gesellschaft, Bad Salzdetfurth, 1994, pp. 90-94.
6. Hamann, B., Hülsenberg, D. and Leutbecher, Th., "Glass Ware Manufactured on the Basis of Culletts Containing Heavy Metal Oxides", *Glastechnische Berichte, Glass Science and Technology*, Vol. 68, No. C2, 1995, pp. 183-190.
7. Handbook of Composites, ed. by G. Lubin, Van Nostrand Reinhold, New York, 1982
8. Loewenstein, K. L., *The Manufacturing Technology of Continuous Glass Fibres*, Elsevier, Amsterdam, London, New York, Tokyo, 1983.
9. Kravtchenko, I., Gorobinskay, V., "Recycling of Electronic Glass Waste", *Materials Engineering*, 1999, (to be published).
10. German Standard DIN 6871 (Part 1), "Cyclotron Systems for Positron-Emission-Tomography; Requirements for Construction Radiation Protection", Beuth Verlag GmbH, Berlin, 1996.
11. Huggins, M. L., Sun, K.-H. and Silverman, A., "The Vitreous State", *The Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 26, No. 12, 1943, pp. 393-398.
12. Ramachandran, B. E., Pai, B. C. and Balasubramanian, N., "Studies on the Acid Resistance of E-glass", *The Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 63, No. 1-2, 1980, pp. 1-3.
13. Ramachandran, B. E., Velpari, V. and Balasubramanian, N., "Chemical Durability Studies on Basalt Fibres", *Journal of Material Science*, No. 16, 1981, pp. 3393-3397.
14. Appen, A.A., *Chemistry of Glass*, Khimia, Moscow, 1979.
15. Mohr, J. G. and Rowe, W. P., *Fiber Glass*, VNR Company, New York, 1978.
16. Rosatto, D. V., and Grove, C. S., *Filament Winding: Its Development, Manufacture, Applications, and Design*, Interscience Publishes, New York, 1964.
17. Handbook of Composites, ed. by D. Karpinos, Naukova Dumka, Kiev, 1985.

18. Cooke, T. F., "Inorganic Fibres - a Literature Review" *The Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 74, No. 12, 1991, pp. 2959-2978.
19. Reichelt, W. and Kunz, R., "Recyclinggerechte Konstruktion mit wiederverwertbaren Werkstoffen", *Ingenieur-Werkstoffe*, Vol. 3, No. 11, 1991, pp. 48-50.
20. Sun, L. L. and Sun, K.-H., "X-Ray Absorption and Transmitting Glasses", *The Glass Industry*, No. 12, 1948, pp. 686-691, 714, 716.
21. Sauter, E., *Grundlagen des Strahlenschutzes*, Karl Thiernig AG, München, 1983.
22. Zimmerman, G., *Strahlenschutz*, Kohlhammer, Stuttgart, 1993.